

From sawdust to packaging and tissue

In view of a circular bioeconomy, we must start rethinking the packaging of products. Biodegradable, non-plastics food packaging and catering products are a good example of environmentally friendly and sustainable products, which can substitute fo. Therefore, it is needed to work with improved take back systems to offer solutions with genuine environmental impact. It is seen as a very profitable together in smart partnerships and in order to optimize value chains. A good example for keeping sawdust biomass in use is presented with sawdust that is treated to special pulps so that it can be used for plastic free packaging. After disposal from the consumer the packaging can be recycled into special kind of tissue. Thereby, resource efficiency can be improved.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Using wood pulp in these applications is better than incineration because resource efficiency can be improved
- ▶ The practice is seen as economically feasible, especially in view of the take back system by which even more packaging can be recycled
- ▶ These practices were enabled by a much effort driving the regulation of the take back system forward
- ▶ Overall, this system can achieve highest market and public acceptance for biodegradable packaging and recycled tissue

Regional coverage and transferability

Packaging from sustainable sources is driven more and more as it is on the one hand on the political agenda and on the other hand demand for packaging without plastics is also seen from consumer side. From this point of view, waste and side-stream valorisation of sawdust for packaging can be seen as economically promising way of upcycling and transferable to other businesses. The presented case of sawdust that is processed into pulp for packaging, which can be used for tissues is a regional case of the Northern macro-region. The network operates at a very regional basis. However, the cascading principles of such case are not regionally dependent.

